

Data Jakarta

	Nama Toko	Spesifikasi	Keterangan
1	Kareem	Oleh-oleh Haji dan umroh	C
2	Arabia	Menjual beragam oleh-oleh haji & umroh terlengkap	PI
3	Al-Madina	Pusat grosir kurma; Grosir & eceran kurma, kacang arab	PI
4	Al-Iqmal Muslim	(Sajadah dll)	C
5	Toko Rezeki	Pusat kurma & oleh-oleh haji	C / Ind
6	Barokah 25	Oleh-oleh haji & umroh	C / Ind
7	Toko Delapan Saudara	Specialis sajadah turkey & local Kain sarung, surban, kain batik, peci	C / Ind
8	Sido mukti jaya	(kain sarung)	C / Ind
9	Toko Do'a Ibu	Grosir & eceran oleh-oleh haji	C / Ind
10	Maju Bersama	The moslem modern wear	C / Ind
11	Rama Sajadah		PN / Ind
12	Toko All Rohmah	(Sajadah)	C
13	Toko Amanah Sarwo Ono	(Kurma dll)	C / Ind-Jw
14	Toko Bintang Kurma	Pusat Distributor Oleh-oleh Haji & Umroh, Terlengkap Grosir dan Eceran	O / Ind
15	Albani	Menjual beragam oleh-oleh haji & umroh	PN
16	Toko Ummy Haekal	Menjual oleh-oleh haji dan umroh	PN
17	Ummy Haekal	Menjual perlengkapan haji dan umroh	PN
18	Toko Ruko 100	Menjual sajadah, sarung, peci, dll	PI
19	Toko Al Fazza	Pusat oleh-oleh haji umroh	PN
20	Dunia Haji	(oleh-oleh haji umroh)	C / Ind
21	Toko Berkah Jaya	Moslem Clothing & Apparel (menjual bermacam-macam perlengkapan dan oleh-oleh haji umroh)	C / Ind
22	DL Busana Muslim	Menjual perlengkapan pakaian haji & umrah	?
23	Adzani	(grosir gamis anak)	PN
24	Ikhwan	(Busana muslim ikhwan)	C
25	Kuda Mas	Busana Muslim	O
26	Firza Moslem Wear		PN / Eng
27	SM (Sigma Muslim) Fashion		C / Eng
28	Buana BWI 188	Grosir Baju Muslim	C / Ind
29	Fina Busana Muslim		PN / Ind
30	3 busana muslim collection		O / Ind
31	Al-Mi'a	(Busana muslim pria)	C
32	Re & Ri	(Busana muslimah)	PN
33	Cantik Boutique	(Gamis premium)	C / Ind

34	Kurnia Jaya	(Pakaian muslim muslimah)	C / Ind
35	Ria Busana	(Gamis, blouse, kebaya)	PN / Ind
36	Attin Collection	(Fashion muslim, gamis)	PN / Eng
37	T.S. Maju Enterprise	(Pakaian muslim ikhwan)	C / Ind
38	Humairra	(Gamis Syar'i set cadar)	PN
39	Hisyam	Pakaian muslim pakistan	PN
40	Khalillah	Pakaian muslim	PN

Data nama-nama biro umroh / haji yang berkantor pusat di Jakarta

	Nama Travel	Keterangan
1	Afi Tour	PN
2	Ahmad Tour	PN
3	Aida Tourindo Wisata	PN
4	Al Ahram Hajj	C
5	Al Amin Tour	C
6	Al Aqsha Jisru Dakwah	PI
7	Al Fauzi Tour	PN
8	Al Hijaz Tour & Travel	PI
9	Al Shafwah Wisata Mandiri	PI
10	Al Wafa	C
11	Alia wisata	PN
12	Alindra Hageem	PN
13	Alsha Tours & Travel	PN
14	Anamta (Annur Maknah Wisata) Tour & Travel	C
15	Arminareka	PI
16	Asy'syifa Travel Umroh	C
17	Dream Tour & Travel	C / Eng
18	Edipeni Tours & Travel	C / Jw
19	El Marwa	PI
20	Elteyba	C
21	Ghifary Travel	PN
22	Hasanah Tours & Travel	C
23	Indah Wisata	C / Ind
24	Inhil Arjuna	PN
25	Jannah Travel	C
26	Khazzanah Al-Anshary	C
27	Maghfirah Travel	C
28	Maktour	PI
29	Multazam Utama Tour	O Spec
30	Muna Tour	C
31	Nurbaitullah Travel	O Spec
32	Nurul Amanah Tour	C
33	Pan Travel	?

34	Qifaya Tour & Travel	PN
35	Rabbani Tour	C
36	Tanur Muthmainnah Tour	C
37	Thayiba Tora Tours & Travel	C
38	Tursina (Tur Silaturahmi Nabi) Tours	PI
39	Umi Tour & Travel	PN
40	Wesal Travel	?

Data Jogja

Umroh & Haji (travel)

1	Patuna	C ('Pemrakarsa, pelopor')
2	Hasuna Tour	PN ('very beautiful')
3	Sahid Tour	PN
4	La Raiba	C ('No doubt' -Quran)
5	Dewangga Lil Hajj wal Umroh	PN ; Local+Arab
6	Darul Umroh Alharamain	PI
7	Surya Citra Madani	C
8	Umroh Jogja Razi Tour & Travel	PN
9	Nabawi Mulia	PI
10	Hajar Aswad Mubaroq	O + C
11	Zhafirah	C ('victorious')
12	Amanah Berkah Mandiri	C
13	Cahaya Imani	C
14	Nur Ramadhan (cabang Jogja)	C
15	Permata Umat	C
16	PT At Tiquu	PN (dari Sutikno)
17	Rihaal Tour	C ('Depart; march')
18	PT As-Shofa Tours	PI
19	Laraiba Tour	C
20	PT Madina Prima Group	C
	Galery Zahira/pendaftaran umroh dan haji plus	PI (Arofah-Mina)
21	Arminareka	
22	Shafa Al Anshor	PI
23	Umroh Jogja Amana Tour & Travel	C
24	Madinah Iman Wisata Jogja	PI+C
25	PT Imtiyaz Rihlata Rohmah (Imtiyaz Tour)	C ('great king')
26	PT. Nur Ramadhan	C
27	At-Tiquu	PN ('Sutikno')
28	Gamalama	PI (nama Gunung)
29	Rozi Tour & Travel	PN
30	Assakinah Flora Umroh	C

31	Genena Tours Yogyakarta	-
32	PT. Baitullah Tiga Kharisma (BATIK Travel)	O + C
33	PT. Berlian Madani Umrah Travel	O
34	Ardhian Umrah dan Haji Plus	PN
35	Luna Amanah	PN
36	Alfajr Tour & Travel	C
37	Al Barokah (Kelompok Bimbingan Haji & Umroh)	C
38	Cahaya Raudhah Indonesia	O PN ('evening conversationalist')
39	Samira	PN
40	Travel Albis Jogja	O
41	Ajwa	PI
42	Alhijaz	PI
43	Al-Madinah	C
44	Khazzanah	C ('great mother')
45	Amma	C
46	PT. Amanah Iman Indonesia	C
47	Nur Muthmainnah	C
48	Mudatama	-
49	Muriz	PN
50	Adzikra	C
51	PT. Al Shafwah Wisata Mandiri	PI
52	Tazkia	C
53	Mubina	C ('clear, distinct')
54	Noor Alia	PN
55	Madina Prima Umroh	PI
56	Ozman	PN
57	Mazaya	PN
58	Aqobah	PI
59	Al Anshor (tur Haji & Umroh, oleh-oleh, dan busana muslim)	C
60	Al Aziziah	PI
61	Iman Madinah	C
62	Al Fatih	PN
63	Aisyiyah	PN
64	Hasto	PN
65	Umrah Babul Ka'bah	O
66	Khibu Bina Umat Yogya	?
67	Madani Tour	PI
68	Al Barakah	C-Konsep

69	An – Nahl	O>Nama Surat Alquran
70	Umroh Haji Furoda	C-Konsep
71	Al Balad	O>Nama surat Al Quran (The City)
72	Biro Travel Umroh Jogja Jafa Tour	PI (Java?)
73	Henira	PN
74	Faraya	PI (Kebun)
75	Bin Tolchah	PN
76	Al Haromain	PI (two holy cities)
77	Shafira	C- ('distinguished')
78	Sahara Kafila	PI
79	Galatama	-
80	Raihan	C = Fragrance= Harum
81	Permata Salsabila	O + PI
82	Munatour	C ('wish')
83	Sifa Al Ikhlas	C ('sincere')
84	Ummara.Id	PN (nama sahabat)
85	Asyra	C ('captivator')
86	Latifa Haramain	C ('gentle, kind') + PI
87	Rayan Grup	C ('Wise, smart')
88	Abu	PN
89	Al Umra	C ('safety')

Umroh & Haji (perlengkapan)

Wahyu -	PN / C
Hajimart	C
Kavaa-Naa (perlengkapan & oleh-oleh haji & umroh)	C ('going in a particular direction')
Salaamaa	C ('
Kaaffah Butik	C
Lutfhi Sajadah (perlengkapan & oleh-oleh haji & umroh)	O
Zain (perlengkapan & oleh-oleh haji & umroh)	PN
Al-Barokah	C
Nur Abidin	C
Az-Zahra	PN

Umroh & Haji (oleh-oleh)

Nur Abidin	C
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Kurma Alif Jogja (distributor kurma & oleh-oleh haji & umroh)	PN
Jazoerah	PI
Abi-f	PN
Ummu Abdurrohlim	PN
Salman	PN
Toko Perlengkapan Haji dan Umroh Oleh-oleh Haji dan Umroh Toko herbal Madinaa	PI
Toko Oleh- Oleh Haji Umroh Sulthan	C
Toko Madinah	PI
Azzahra	PN
Nur Fajr	C
Fenham - toko oleh-oleh Umroh & kado pernikahan	?
Kurmanis Jogja (Dates Store)	O (Kurma manis)
Khoir	C
Joglo Muslim Marwah Oleh-oleh Haji dan Umroh	C
SalMan (Salma Mandiri)	PN

Pengobatan

Alfasdhu Jogja - Tabib Roy	PN
Aswaja (bekam)	C
Rumah Sehat Raudhotusyifa	C
Klinik Terapi Sehat Darul Afiat	PI
Bekam pak Wahab	PN
Bekam Syariah Umar Bin Khattab	PN
Griya Terapi Alkayyis	C ('kebijaksanaan')
bekam Alhijamah Pak Ismadi	PN
Bekam Nahmed	PN
Bekam & Akupunktur Khusus Wanita Griya Sehat Ayu Muslimah Nabila	PN
Anabill Hijama – bekam	PN
Bekam ruqyah syariyyah	C
Bekam Jogja & Ruqyah Syar'iyah "AsySyifa Holy Holistic"	C
Al-Hijamah (Bekam Medis)	C
Griya Sehat Al-Wahida – Bekam	C
Bekam Akhwat Auraa	C
Bekam Aswaja	C
Klinik Bekam Sunan Giri Al Khijamah	PN
Azzahwa Bekam dan herbal	C ('Kesegaran')
Bekam & Pijat Masjid Baiturrahim	PI
Klinik Bekam Al Khijamah Bapak Rujito	PN

Bekam dan Herbal "Asy-Syifa"	C
Roemah Fadliya (akupuntur, bekam, releksi, dll.)	PN
Klinik Bekam Dan Herbal Awaliyah Syifa	C ('permulaan kesembuhan')
Bekam Nur-Asyifa Mrisi Indah	C
Bekam dan Herbal Awaliyah Syifa	C ('permulaan kesembuhan')
Klinik Akupunktur Hikari	-
Rumah Bekam Amin	PN
Bekam, Totok, Gurah, Ruqyah kang Nur Kholid	PN
Worldwide Rhizoma Pusat Bekam & Pengobatan Herbal	Eng - Object
Hijamah - bekam sunnah	C
Pondok Ruqyah & Bekam Sunah Ar-Ridho	C
Klinik Bekam "Herba Syfa"	C
Bekam As Salam	C
Bekam Ar Rosyid	C
Gurah & Bekam (Bpk.Aziz Wahyudin)	PN
Terapi Gurah dan bekam Roziyah	PN
Bekam Al Mujarobatt Terapi	C ('Mujarab')
Al Fashdu Bantul	C
Pijat & Bekam Cak Yanto Sholehuddin	PN
Gurah & Bekam Al Hijamah	C
Rumah Bekam Ummu Hema	PN
Griya Ruqyah Syar'iyah	C
Khasanah Therapy (Akupunktur dan Bekam Homecare)	C
Baitur Ruqyah Asy- Syar'iyah Wal Hijamah	C
Klinik Pratama D'Maryam	PN
Athif Herba Syifa - Bekam & Gurah	PN
Sumarto (Zaid Herbal & Bekam)	PN
Griya Sehat Syifauka	C (prayer)
Klinik Sehat Mugi Barokah	Prayer
Griya Sehat El Syifa	PN
Terapi Bekam Al Faruq	PN
Thibbunnabawi Jogja - Bekam dll.	C
Griya Bekam - Pondok Al Qur'an Muntiyamah	PI (affiliated)
Rumah Bekam An-nur	C

Busana

Zayn

Pands

Most of them use female Name

PN

?

Rabbani	C
Pusat Perbelanjaan Khasanah Muslim Al Fath	C
Baju Muslimah Luvia	PN
Maulana	PN / Title
Annisa	PN
An-Nur	C
Al-Shukran	C
Karita Moslem Square	PN
Adeeva	PN
Zam-Zam	O
Luvana	PN
Zakia Hijab & Muslim Wear	PN
Al Zafara Moslem Syar'i Store	C
Griya Muslim Kayla	PN
Griya Muslim Khayla	PN
Saffanah Gerai Muslim Olshop	PN
Toko Ana	PN
Syaqilla	PN
Syar'ie	C
Razka Jogja Pusat Sembako & Mikihat Jogja	PN
Dhawy Muslim Gallery	C ('very spiritual')
Khazanah Butik	C
Fatimah Muslim	PN
Ubudiyah Baju nikah Muslimah dan Kavaya hijab	C
Ummiajwad	PN
Rellia Boutique	PN
Toko Baju Aji Testing	PN
Amanah	C
elzatta hijab	PN
Nafisah Galeri	PN
Nasywa	PN
Azkiya	PN
Aisya hijab style	PN
Nissa	PN
Sabilla FA	PN
Agazo	PN
Alvaretta	PN
Sabiya	PN
Yasmine Store	PN
Ihya	PN (male) = revival; giving life

Fadkhera	PN
Sharie	C
Lubna Collection	PN
Rima Casualsyari	PN
Sevilla grosir gamis dan mukena yogya	PI
Griya Busana Muslim Assyifa	PN
Raihah	PN
Safin	PN
Alysha Hijab	PN
Toko Baju Renang Danisha Distro Jogja	PN
Ghazara	PN (female) =gift
Syarie Butik Muslimah	PN
Ridho	PN (male) / C
Gaia Fashion	C (fr gaya)
Safa	PN
Al Husna	C
Azzam	PN / C
Grosir gamis xansadam collection	PN
Annur Butik	C
Barakah grosir Sarung sorban sajadah dan busana muslim	C
Nadiya	PN
Arina Boutique	PN
V-ra Rumah Produksi	PN
Arrahman Moslem Wear	C
Anie fashion	PN
Najwan Collection	PN ('saved, liberated')
Al Fatih	PN / C
Toko Busana Muslim Syafa Shop dan Sahabat Air Amanah	PN
Gerai Hijab Fatima	PN
Toko Ya Akhi	Address
Firdaus Hijab	PI
Arsya	PN
Humaira	PN
Ramadhani Collection	C
Kiswah	O
Nouri	PN
Distributor Koko Ahzaravy	PN
Elita Kerudung	PN
El Mahabbah	C

Toko Buku dan Busana Muslim Ahcsunnah	C
Lulu Lutfi Labibi	PN
De' Khayla Boutique	PN
Jubah Akhwat	C
Al-Afasy	C = seeker of truth
Maxmarastore	PN
Kharida	PN
Kamila	PN
Ameera Kerudung	PN
Dannis	PN
Jazirah Middle Eastern Store	Pl
Nibras House	O = lamp/light
Hafa Busana	PN = guardian, protector
Nazeera	PN
Maysura	PN
Mardha	PN
Yuni Busana	PN
Rumini	PN
Dafitri	PN
Alda	PN
Hamuna	PN
Muhsin	PN

Data Pakistan: Peshawar, Islamabad, Rawalpindi

PESHAWAR :

	Name	Field	Referent	Remark
	Alharam	herbal pharma	Pl	City
	Arafat	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	a vast open space for Hajj
	Makkah	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	City
	Al Madina	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	City
	Imarat	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	A place in Uni-Arab Emirate
	Haqqani	book shop	Pl	Islamic University in Pakistan
	Darul Nouman	book shop	Pl	Founder of Hanafi school of thought.
	Deoband	book shop	Pl	(referring to Islamic university in India)
	Haqqania	book shop	Pl	referring to Islamic university in Pakistan

	Inam	Dawakhana	C	Reward; dispensary
	Alkhidmat	unani dawakhana	C	Help; Greek dispensary
	Alrehab	khusboo Mahal	C	Welcome
	Aldeen	Khushboo Mahal	C	Religion
	Alhuda	Hajj & Umrah Services	C	heavenly guidance
	Islamic	book shop	C	
	Islamic	publishers	C	
	Wahidia	book shop	C	referring to oneness of Allah
	Islami	book shop	C	
	Bin Iman	Collection	C	the believers
	Religious	book shop	C	
	Faiz ul Quran	book shop	C	seeking guidance from Quran
	Islami	bookshop	C	
	Deeni	bookshop	C	Religious
	Islamic center	bookshop	C	
	Islah	bookshop	C	self-purification
	islamic	knowledge center	C	
	Rahmania	book shop	C	the blessing of Allah Almighty
	EDEN	ROBE	C	the second stage of paradise
	Iqra	book shop		to Read, that was the first revelation
	Qari	Khushboo Mahal	Profesion	Quran reciter
	Salah Din	Khushboo Mahal	Prof	Islamic Warrior
	Al zahid	Khushboo Mahal	Prof	Pious Person
	KHORFAKKAN	Hajj & Umrah Services	Prof	Facilitator
	Zam Zam	Khushboo Mahal	O	
	Kaaba	Khushboo Mahal	O	
	Mushk	Khushboo Mahal	O	Fragrance from male deer
	Al-Manaraat	Hajj & Umrah Services	O	Minaret
	Ihram	Hajj & Umrah Services	O	specific religious dress for performing hajj and umra
	Noor ul Quran	palace bookshop	O -spc	the light of holy Quran

	Anwar ul Quran	bookshop	O -spc	the lightnings of Holy Quran
	Taj ul Quran	bookshop	O -spc	the throne of holy Quran
	Al-Badar	Trading Estblishment	E	the 1st islamic battle in Badar
	Albadar	Khushboo Mahal	E	Islamic war Badar,
	Habibia	book shop	Q	beloved one
	Ajmal	Khushboo Mahal	Q	the most beautiful
	Al kareem	Islamic research center	Q	
	Al-Sudais	Travels & Tours for Hajj and Umrah operators	PN	Imam e Kaaba
	Qasimi	book shop	PN	
	Abubakar	book shop	PN	the first Islamic caliph
	Umar Farooq	book shop	PN	the second Islamic caliph
	Usman Ghani	bookshop	PN	the third Islamic caliph
	Imam-e Muhammad	bookshop	PN	the student of Imam Abu Hanifa
	Farooq e Azam	bookshop	PN	the second Islamic caliph

RAWALPINDI

	Name	Field	Referent	
	Madina	Medical Complex	Pl	
	Makkah	Restaurant	Pl	
	Bain ul Haramain	travels and Tours Agency	Pl	the center of Makka and Madina
	Al Aqsa	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	referring to a famous Islamic mosque
	Al haramain	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	
	ALMadina	Khushboo Mahal	Pl	
	Al-Madina	refreshment hotel	Pl	
	Madina zia	Prayer mates	Pl	
	Makka	cloth house	Pl	

	Makkah	Perfume center	PI	
	Jaddah	Carpets	PI	
	Al Imarat	Khushboo Mahal	PI	
	Qadria	sweets and Bakers	C	one of the tributary of sufism
	Alharam	Carpet Store	C	the respected one
	Alharam	Girls Hostel	C	
	Chishti	Clothes and Garments	C	one of the tributary of Sufism
	Chishti	Consultants	C	
	Chishti	Fresh flower shop	C	
	Marhaba	Khushboo Mahal	C	
	Al fajr	Khushboo Mahal	C	referring to a sura in Quran
	Labaik	Khushboo Mahal	C	to respond in a good manner
	Taqwa	prayers mate and Ahram center	C	
	Ma Sha Allah	crookery	C	
	Deen	Fabrics	C	
	Rahman	medical store	C	
	Alnoor	Chemist	C	
	Al- Razzaq	pharmacy	C	the sustanenance
	Alkhair	bag house	C	the betterment
	Bismillah	special qulfi	C	referring to the islamic words used for starting anything
	Bismillah	sweet shop	C	
	Taqwa	Hajj & Umrah Services	C	Piety
	Labbaik	Services Pvt Ltd for hajj and umra	C	Arabic word used for the reply and to be present
	Allah-U-Akbar	Hajj & Umrah Services Private Limited	C	Referring To The Greatness Of Allah
	Bismillah	Hotel	C	Arabic word used for starting work
	Muslim	General Store	C	
	Al Janat	Mall	C	Paradise
	Alharam	jewellers	C	
	Noor-ul-Harmain	Travels & Tours	C	light of Makkah and Madina

	Al Balagh	Islamic Store	Prof	referring to preaching
	Hafiz	General Store Garments	Prof	the one who remembered the Holy Quran
	Abdullah Brothers	Ahram center for hajj and umra	PN	
	Abubakar	Bridel gallery		
	AL safron (زعفران)	Khushboo Mahal	O	
	Al-Hateem	International Travel (Pvt) Ltd	O	referring to a place in Makkah
	Mutaff	Hajj Umra Services	O	place in kaaba
	Karwan-e-Izhar- ul-Islam	Hajj & Umrah Services Pvt Ltd	O	Caravan for showing Islam
	Karwan e Makkah	(Pvt) Ltd	O	
	Karwan e Labbaik	Hajj & Umrah Services (Pvt) Ltd	O	
	Karwan-e-Hubbe Rasool		O	caravan of Love of Holy Prophet saw
	Al Baddar	Hotel	E	referring to the first Islamic battle

ISLAMABAD

	Name	Field	Referent	
	Madina	electronics	Pl	A city in Saudi Arabia
	Madina	clothes	Pl	
	Madina	Lab and Diagnostic Center	Pl	
	Al-Harmain	Travel & Tourism Agency	Pl	referring to Makka and Madina
	Al-Makkah	International	Pl	
	Almadina	cloth shop	Pl	
	Al Madina	Cloth store	Pl	
	Madina	Pansar Store And Dawakhana, Abpara	Pl	

	Abu Sufyan	Maktaba and khushboo Mahal	PN	
	Ghazi Shaheed	Maktaba & khubooo Mehal	PN	
	Shaheed Islam	Maktaba	PN	
	Marhabba	super store	C	referring to Islamic greetings
	Mashallah	general store	C	wish of Allah
	Al-Raheem	Travels	C	blessing of Allah Almighty
	Baarik	Travel & Tours (Private) Limited	C	The Blessing
	Waqar-E-Madinah	Travel & Tours	C	The Dignity Of Madina
	Bab-Ur-Raheem	Travel & Tours Private Limited	C	The Door Of Blessing
	Safr E Ibadat	Travels & Tours	C	the journey toward worshipping
	The Heaven Explorers		C	
	Taqwa	Hajj & Umrah Services (Pvt) Ltd	C	the piety
	Alhuda	International Travel Tours	C	The Righteous Guidance
	Muslim kaamil	Shop	C	the perfect muslim
	Islamic Trends	Religious book store	C	
	Albaraka	Perfumes	C	
	Muslim	Pansar Store	C	
	Muslim	Fair Price Shop	C	
	Darussalam	Islamic Store	C	
	Bismillah	Hotel	C	
	Al-Muslim	Store	C	
	AlBalagh	Islamic Store	Prof	
	AlBalagh	Islamic Store	Prof	the preacher
	AL-FURQAN	international (pvt) ltd	O	Arabic name of the holy Quran
	Hijab e Fatmiya		O	the veil of hazrat Fatima RA
	Mutaaf e kaaba	travel & tours	O spec	the place in the center of kaaba

	ZAM ZAM	tibbi dawakhana & pansar store	O	
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